

Co-UDlabs

Building Collaborative Urban Drainage
research Labs communities

D3.3. 3rd Report on training and education activities

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Background: about the Co-UDlabs Project

Co-UDlabs is an EU-funded project aiming to integrate research and innovation activities in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) to address pressing public health, flood risks and environmental challenges.

Bringing together 17 unique research facilities, Co-UDlabs offers training and free access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in Urban drainage systems.

Co-UDlabs aims to create a urban drainage large-scale facilities network to provide opportunities for monitoring water quality, UDS performance and smart and open data approaches.

The main objective of the project is to provide a transnational multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure that will allow stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage water sector to come together, share ideas, co-produce project concepts and then benefit from access to top-class research infrastructures to develop, improve and demonstrate those concepts, thereby building a collaborative European Urban Drainage innovation community.

The initiative will facilitate the uptake of innovation in traditional buried pipe systems and newer green-blue infrastructure, with a focus on increasing the understanding of asset deterioration and improving system resilience.

List of acronyms

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
AaU	University of Aalborg
CA	Consortium Agreement
CITEEC	Center for Technological Innovation in Construction and Civil Engineering
DEL	Deltares
ECTS	European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System
ESR	Early-Stage Researcher
FTIR	Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy
GA	Grant Agreement
IKT	Institute for Underground Infrastructure
INSA	National Institute of Applied Sciences
JRA	Joint Research Activity
LIDAR	Airborne light detection and ranging
RI	Research Infrastructure
SfM	Structure from motion
TA	Transnational Access
UD/UDS	Urban Drainage / Urban Drainage System
UDC	University of A Coruña
USFD	University of Sheffield
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document is a deliverable of the Co-UDlabs project, funded under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008626.

This is the 3rd and final report on training and education activities organized by the project partners under WP3, that included: UD early-stage researcher activities and training events, UD professionals and practitioners training activities, public webinars and educations activities.

Through the organization of these events, WP3’s objectives are to:

- Enhance the transfer of knowledge and develop new skills among the project partners and between the research community and the practitioner’s community;
- Foster the use of the Co-UDlabs Research Infrastructures via tailored actions targeting their future users;
- Create a pool of high-qualified professionals via adequate training activities targeted to general Urban Drainage community, with a special attention to increase the participation of the industry and the early-stage researchers’ community.

1. The Co-UDlabs training programme

In support of its research activities and the establishment of a pan-European Network for Urban Drainage Innovation, Co-UDlabs organised a series of training activities and initiatives, as part of WP3. The project's training strategy is based on three main pillars:

- UD early-stage and junior researchers' activities and training events (Task 3.1)
- UD industry professionals and practitioners training activities (Task 3.2)
- Public webinars on specific and emerging monitoring techniques in UD (Task 3.3)

These events took place in a hybrid, online or physical format.

A dedicated page of the website was dedicated to provide all the necessary information regarding past and future training events: <https://co-udlabs.eu/networking/training/>. These were also systematically promoted on the project social media and by the project partners in their websites and to their professional contact networks.

Whenever possible, these trainings were recorded and have been made available online on the Co-UDlabs **YouTube channel** (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC29ggHMkX1w9QReChDcXniQ>). The Co-UDlabs YouTube channel gathers the content of the webinars and other training actions related with specific monitoring techniques such as optical imaging, microplastics monitoring, drainage assets assessment, uncertainty analysis. It is curated by the project consortium and is regularly being updated with videos from the project, allowing the community to access the project content during and after the project completion.

1.1. UD early-stage and junior researchers' activities and training events

Two types of activities were planned within this pillar:

1. **Two internal Co-UDlabs early-stage researcher seminars** targeting PhDs and early-stage researchers from partner institutions of Co-UDlabs, aiming to enhance interaction between academics, sharing ideas and promote common experimental protocols. These seminars had a duration of 2 days and were targeting 20 participants.
2. **One open workshop and one PhD course** targeting the UD European junior research community.

The following training events were organised during the project lifetime to train UD junior and early-stage researchers:

Two internal Co-UDlabs early-stage researcher seminars:

- The first Co-UDlabs early-stage researcher seminar took place on June 27-28, 2022, at the UDC's School of Civil Engineering in A Coruña (Spain). The seminar aimed to enhance interactions between PhD students and junior researchers of the project, sharing ideas while identifying and promoting common experimental protocols and approaches. Organised by UDC, the seminar was an excellent opportunity for everybody to learn about the project's main research lines and agendas and receive feedback, recommendations, and additional insight. The event included cutting-edge work and presentations on sediment accumulation, wastewater turbidity monitoring, infrastructural planning for heavy-rain laboratories, as well as innovative approaches to flooding health risks, performance assessment in UDS, LIDAR and SfM-based techniques for surveying and experimental planning. A total number of 9 oral presentation were performed in the seminar

which accounts with the participation of 33 attendees. The agenda of the event is available in Annex 1. More information is available on the project website (<https://co-udlabs.eu/2022/07/04/co-udlabs-celebrated-its-first-general-assembly-and-early-stage-researchers-seminar/>).

Figure 1: 1st Co-UDlabs internal early-stage researcher seminar

- The second Co-UDlabs early-stage researcher seminar was organized by the University of Sheffield on September 19-20, 2024. Speakers included academics from the University of Sheffield (Simon Tait, Kaml Birdi, Alma Schellart, Henriette Jensen and James Shucksmith) and external experts from commercial organisations (Pete Skipworth from CuraTerrae and Sam Shelley from Nuron). Topics included developing commercial products, industrial career routes and pathways, the development and implementation of innovation and guidance on academic career routes and innovation funding. Seven attendees participated in person from a range of UK and overseas institutions.

Figure 2: Co-UDlabs internal early-stage research seminar in Sheffield

Three open workshops and PhD courses:

- A **PhD course on Sewer Processes with focus on hydrogen sulfide modelling and management** was organized by AaU in Aalborg (Denmark) on October 7-11, 2024. It was worth 5 credits in the ECTS system and was open to PhD students from institutions from all over Europe. Attended by 9 students, the course focused on sewer process and sewer process modelling in relation to sulfide and methane formation and associated problems in terms of odor sewer corrosion and greenhouse emissions. The objective of the course was to give the students insight and knowledge on the most recent advances of sewer process modelling and applications to real-world use. The course addressed the following topics:

- State-of-the-art of the sewer process modeling
- Aerobic and anaerobic organic matter transformation
- Air-water mass transfer of sewer gases
- Sewer odor and corrosion
- Mitigation methods

The flyer of the event is available in Annex 2 and on the Co-UDlabs website (<https://co-udlabs.eu/evenements/phd-course-on-sewer-processes-with-focus-on-hydrogen-sulfide-modeling-and-management/>).

Figure 3: PhD course on Sewer Processes in Aalborg

- The **25th EJSW – European Junior Scientists Workshop on “Monitoring Urban Drainage Systems and Rivers”** was held on 15-21 May 2022, in St-Maurice-en-Valgaudemar, France. This workshop was jointly organised by the Sewer Systems and Processes Working Group of the IWA/IAHR Joint Committee on Urban Drainage and the Co-UDlabs project. It gathered 20 junior-scientist participants from institutions based in 11 countries and even more diverse nationalities. The 25th EJSW included:

- 20 oral presentations by the junior scientists (20 min presentation + 10 min for questions/answers).
- 5 short courses (45 min) by senior organisers on i) low-cost monitoring, ii) uncertainty assessment, iii) data validation, iv) application of cameras in discharge monitoring, and v) 3D-printing applied to urban drainage and river monitoring.
- 1 workshop (1.5 h) on ethics in science and research.
- 4 afternoon hands-on sessions: In total 8 sessions were organized and each participant attended one of them: (i) DIY low-cost water level monitoring, ii) sediment transport monitoring, iii) tracing experiment for discharge measurement, iv) data validation, v) sensor calibration, vi) uncertainty assessment, vii) Large-Scale Particle Image Velocimetry (LSPIV) in river flows, and viii) turbidity -TSS (or COD) correlation.

The EJSW benefited from wonderful weather for outdoor hands-on sessions and was a great opportunity for sharing knowledge and experience, networking and creating links between participants, reinforced by recreational activities. The flyer of the event is available in Annex 3. More information is available on the project website (<https://co-udlabs.eu/2022/05/26/25th-ejsw-2022/>).

Figure 4: EJSW 2022 in St Maurice en Valgaudemar (photo: F. Clemens-Meyer)

- The **26th EJSW – European Junior Scientists Workshop on “Monitoring UDS and Rivers”** was held on May 26 – June 1, 2024, in St-Maurice-en-Valgaudemar, France. This workshop was organized by INSA Lyon and Deltares (Co-UDlabs partners), in collaboration with the Sewer Systems & Processes Working Group of the IWA – IAHR Joint Committee on Urban Drainage. It focused on on-line monitoring of water quality and quantity in waste- and stormwater collection systems, and rivers; Links between data validation and model calibration; Emerging monitoring concepts and data communication techniques; Ethics in researching, publishing, presenting and sharing data. It gathered 20 junior-scientist participants from institutions based in 10 countries. The 26th EJSW included:
 - 20 oral presentations by the junior scientists (20 min presentation + 10 min for questions/answers).
 - 6 lectures (45 min) by senior organisers on: i) River morphology, ii) Remote sensing and optical observations in hydraulic structures. iii) Data validation and sensor calibration, iv) 3D printing and design for manufacturing sensors, v) Transport processes and monitoring floating materials (Plastics and FOG). vi) FAIR data, publishing, and open data

- 1 workshop (1.5 h) on ethics in science and research
- 1 guided-field visit (4.5 h) to hydrogeology alpine formations by Dr. Marianna Jagercikova
- In total 8 sessions (2 in parallel) were organized (each participant could select 4 of them): (i) Geophone based riverine morphology measurements, ii) Uncertainty analysis for monitoring data, iii) Cameras/drones as a measuring tool, discharge estimates in open channel flows iv) data validation workshop, v) Sediment size distribution monitoring and structure from motion measurements, vi) sensor calibration workshop, vii) tracer experiments for discharge estimation, and viii) Stone tracking with RFID and Geophone data analysis.

The call for abstracts and the brochure of the event are available on Annex 4 and on the Co-UDlabs website (<https://co-udlabs.eu/2023/08/29/26th-european-junior-scientists-workshop-ejsw-call-for-abstracts/>), with all information related to the workshop available on the event website (<https://ejsw-2024.sciencesconf.org/>).

Figure 5: EJSW 2024 in St Maurice en Valgaudemar (photo: F. Clemens-Meyer)

1.2. UD industry professionals and practitioners training activities

This pillar concerns the organisation of training activities aimed specifically at urban drainage industry stakeholders, regulators, professionals and practitioners of UDS and local utility managers.

- The first of these events was organized by IKT on November 3-4, 2021. The free online **Workshop on Urban Drainage Practice and Research Needs** aimed to identify valuable good practices and research for the optimisation of UD assets' performance and improve their resilience to climate change and sustainability. More specifically, the workshop was also designed to introduce Co-UDlabs' three Joint Research Activities and to illustrate their themes with various examples of issues and good practices from urban drainage network owners and researchers. It was, in other words, a very valuable and outstanding opportunity for researchers, utility management, regulators, businesses, and other relevant stakeholders in UD systems to meet, discuss, and share potential pathbreaking ideas for the sustainable future of this field. The workshop was also a great venue to introduce Co-UDlabs' first Trans-National Access (TA) call to the attendees. The workshop was attended by 59 participants on Day1 and 51 participants on Day2. The agenda of the workshop is available in Annex 5. All presentations are available for download on the project website (<https://co-udlabs.eu/2021/11/09/ikt-workshop/>).

- **Industrial workshop on flow rate determination of pumping stations and hydraulic structures** (DEL - November 17, 2022). This one-day course was on “Capacity problems and flow rate determination in pressurized systems”. With 58 participants, the webinar targeted practitioners who are either designing, building, or managing wastewater pressure mains. The following subjects were addressed in the course: 1) Basics of (multiphase) hydraulics in pressurized systems 2) How to determine the performance of a pressurized system and to detect capacity problems 3) Different sources of capacity problems and how to identify them 4) The effect of air/gas pockets on capacity, energy consumption and what remedies are available 5) Methods to detect the presence of air/gas pockets 6) Several relevant case studies. The workshop is fully available on the Co-UDlabs website and Youtube channel (<https://co-udlabs.eu/2022/11/30/lets-take-a-look-back-at-the-co-udlabs-industrial-workshop-capacity-problems-flow-rate-determination-in-pressurized-systems/>). The agenda is available in Annex 6.

Figure 6: Industrial workshop organised by Deltares

- On October 17, 2023, Co-UDlabs was at the 7th edition of the Spanish Water Engineering Days (VII Jornadas de Ingeniería del Agua, JIA), where Co-UDlabs’ partners at the Universidade da Coruña hosted a session to introduce the **Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox** (UDMT), an online and open-access tool developed by INSA Lyon, with a few practical examples of its range and potential. The 13 participants were trained on the fundamentals of the UDMT tool and could participate in two practical exercises on Analysis of real data from a meter with remote reading and on Analysis of real data from a continuous turbidity probe. The agenda is available in Annex 7.

Figure 7: UDMT workshop organised by UDC at the 2023 Spanish Water Engineering Days

- **Industrial and water professional workshop on Uncertainty assessment in UD monitoring data** (INSA and GRAIE – 6-7 March 2024). With a duration of 2 days, the course targeted practitioners, operators, water

utilities and stakeholders engaged in monitoring activities. The workshop aimed to introduce the importance of uncertainty assessment in urban drainage, present the UDMT webapp, and provide examples of application. A session was fully dedicated to examples and case studies brought by the participants. At the end of the course, participants knew the methods applied in the UDMT and how to use it for their own needs. The training course was attended by seven participants (4 researchers and 3 industrial water system operators) from France, Spain, and Belgium. Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski from INSA Lyon was the main lecturer. The flyer of the workshop, including the programme, is available in Annex 8 and on the Co-UDlabs website (<https://co-udlabs.eu/evenements/workshop-on-uncertainty-assessment-in-urban-drainage/>).

Figure 8: Industrial and water professional workshop organised by INSA and GRAIE

- **Applied course on Urban Drainage metrology (UDC – July 16-19, 2024).** This course targeted UD practitioners and water utilities interested in monitoring the main hydraulic and water quality parameters of sewers and drainage networks. The course was held at CITEEC - Research & Innovation Centre on Civil Engineering laboratories, allowing the participants to join STREET and BLOCK TA infrastructures, as well as Campus-SUDS research infrastructure of UDC on pilot Sustainable Urban Drainage techniques (<https://campus-suds.udc.es/h>). With 21 participants, the course took place over 4 days:
 - Day 1 – Measurement of hydraulic variables. Rainfall, flow rates, water depths and velocities were measured using different technologies (direct measurement, ultrasound, pressure, acoustic velocimetry, etc.).
 - Day 2 – Measurement of pollution parameters. Automatic grab samplers and on-line probes were used to measure the most relevant variables and methods of analysis.
 - Day 3 – Data collection and management. In this session different technologies to convert signals to data were presented. Additionally, the course presented how parametrize hydraulic and pollution parameters linked to dry and wet weather flows.
 - Day 4 – Demo Day – Simulation of a field campaign in the infrastructure of CITEEC. A field work was simulated in the BLOCK model and SUDS pilot techniques. Measurements of all relevant

parameters were made, online and by grab samples. The analyzed events were parameterized assuming that the control sections are part of a specific urban area.

The course was a great opportunity for partners and stakeholders from Spain's and Galicia's communities of academics, researchers, practitioners, utility managers, local UD and water management authorities to meet and share expertise, common issues, and innovative solutions and ideas on a very sensitive topic for public policy and sustainability action. The flyer including the agenda of the Applied course is available in Annex 9.

Figure 9: Applied course on UD metrology organized by UDC

The last workshop aimed for UD industry professionals is planned to take place in March 2025 and it is currently being organised by IKT. The aim of this one-day workshop, which is taking place online, is to use results from the Transnational Access projects to exchange ideas and to define research need regarding the application of practical solutions for the improvement of the monitoring and inspection of drainage systems, which will have an impact on better and more efficient UDS management procedures. This practice workshop will offer a platform for the exchange of knowledge and experience between industry and public sewer network operators, promoting mutual understanding between scientists, industry and network operators.

1.3. Public webinars on specific and emerging monitoring techniques

Each research institution of the project was in charge of organising a webinar for specific and emerging monitoring techniques in UD, as summarised in the table below.

Webinar title	Date	Partners in charge	Status
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1 - FTIR Chemical mapping	21-09-2022	AaU	Completed
2 - Acoustic turbidity measurements	16-05-2023	EAWAG, UDC	Completed
3 - Routine uncertainty assessment (UA) in urban drainage data	12-06-2023	INSA, DEL, GRAIE	Completed
4 – Optical and computer vision techniques for flow and processes	15-03-2024	DEL, UDC	Completed
5 - Routine data validation (DV) in urban drainage	10-01-2025	INSA, GRAIE	Scheduled, on track
6 - Underground infrastructure monitoring techniques	30-01-2025	IKT, UoS, DEL	Scheduled, on track

The last two webinars have been delayed compared to the initial schedule, but organisation has started and is currently ongoing.

The first webinar, focused on **Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) chemical mapping**, was organized by Aalborg University on September 21, 2022. This free webinar was intended to provide basic knowledge on a widely used analytical technique that combines the chemical information from Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy with the resolving power of microscopy. After introducing basic concepts about Infrared Spectroscopy and how an FTIR spectrometer works, infrared microscopy was briefly explained, including different modes of collecting spectra at the microscopic scale. Finally, μ FTIR-chemical mapping technology was introduced, focusing on theoretical and practical details related to this technique. To conclude, the webinar provided a short overview of the main applications of μ FTIR-chemical mapping ranging from biomedical science to material science and microplastic analysis on environmental samples, focusing on urban water microplastic monitoring. This public webinar was attended by 18 participants. The agenda of the webinar is available in Annex 10. The webinar has been recorded and the video has been made available on the project You Tube channel: [Co-UDlabs Webinar: Fourier Transform Infrared Micro-Spectroscopy \(FTIR\) \[Part 2/2\] \(youtube.com\)](#).

Figure 10: Webinar on FTIR chemical mapping (September 21, 2022)

The second webinar on **the principles and applications of acoustic backscattering to monitor suspended solids in natural and engineered systems** was organized by EAWAG on May 16, 2023, from 13:00 -16:30 CEST. As acoustic monitoring in water systems is very contemporary topic, the event was endorsed by the International Water Association and the Association of Hydraulic Research. The event brought together particle experts, sensor manufacturers, and individuals with practical experience in monitoring campaigns and projects. More than 100 participants registered for the event, with around 50 attendants permanent. The webinar was divided into two main blocks of presentations, followed by group discussions and. The presentations cover various aspects, including

particle characterization, problem setting, theory, scattering, and scientific instruments. The afternoon session focuses on applications in urban and wastewater systems. The flyer including the agenda of the webinar is available in Annex 11. The webinar has been recorded and the video has been made available on the project YouTube channel: [CoUDlabs Webinar: Acoustic monitoring of suspended solids in natural and engineered systems \(youtube.com\)](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=...). A summary and the slides of the event are also available in the Co-UDlabs Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7969766>;

Figure 11: Webinar on the principles and applications of acoustic backscattering to monitor suspended solids in natural and engineered systems (May 16, 2023)

The third webinar on **Routine Uncertainty Assessment**, was organized on **June 12, 2023** (14:00 – 16:30 CEST) by INSA and Deltares. The goal was to introduce the importance of uncertainty assessment in urban drainage and the necessity to develop its systematic application, present the methods applied in the UDMT as well as the webapp, and provide examples of application. The speakers were: Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski, Mathieu Lepot (INSA Lyon) & François Clemens (Deltares, TU Delft). With 35 participants, the webinar was recorded and the video made available on the Co-UDlabs YouTube channel: [Co-UDlabs webinar on the Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox \(UDMT\) \(youtube.com\)](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=...).

Figure 12: Webinar on Routine Uncertainty Assessment (June 12, 2023)

The fourth webinar on **Optical and computer vision techniques for flow and processes measurements** was organised on **March 15, 2024** (9:30-11:45 CET) by University of A Coruña and Deltares. This webinar presented

recent advances in the application of optical imaging techniques for monitoring water quantity/quality dynamics and hydraulic structures, and several state-of-the-art large-scale PIV techniques for flow estimations in rivers, urban infrastructure and different AI-assisted data processing routines to extract information on the hydro-environment. The agenda of the webinar is available in Annex 12. The speakers were: Antonio Moreno-Rodenas (Deltares), Juan Naves (Universidade da Coruña), Hessel Winsemius (Rainbow Sensing), Salvador Peña (Photrack), Giulio Dolcetti (University of Trento), Simon Tait (University of Sheffield), Joao Leitao (ETH/EAWAG) and Pierre Lechevallier (EAWAG). With 25 participants, the webinar was recorded and the video made available on the Co-UDlabs YouTube channel: [CoUDlabs Webinar: Optical observations in urban water systems and rivers](#).

Figure 13: Webinar on Optical and computer vision techniques for flow and processes measurements (March 15, 2024)

More information on these events is available on the project website (<https://co-udlabs.eu/networking/training/>). The recordings of past webinars is available on the YouTube channel of the project (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC29ggHMkX1w9QReChDcXniQ>) and was disseminated on the project social media channels for maximum visibility.

2. Conclusions

All training activities planned in the GA were effectively implemented in the framework of WP3. At M44, Co-UDlabs partners have organised 14 successful events: 2 internal Co-UDlabs early-stage researcher seminars, 2 open workshops and 1 PhD course, 5 events targeting UD industry professionals and 4 public webinars.

These trainings allowed the consortium to reach out to a various range of audiences, from students to researchers, industrials and practitioners, and get them to know and use the techniques and tools developed by the projects, thus enhancing the transfer of knowledge and developing new skills between the project partners, the research community and the practitioners.

All the webinar recordings have been uploaded to the Co-UDlabs YouTube Channel where they will remain available for free, even after the end of the project.

In addition, to conclude the training programme, three events are planned to be organized in 2025: the UD industry professional & practitioners training workshop (March 2025) and 2 webinars (January 2025). These will be reported in the third periodic technical report due at the end of the project (M48).

Below is a list of some minor deviations, that did not impact other activities of the project:

- Due to the low number of registrants, the PhD course on Sewer Processes planned to be organized in 2023 by AaU in Aalborg (Denmark) was rescheduled to take place on October 7-11, 2024.
- The Industrial and water professional workshop on Uncertainty assessment in UD monitoring data planned to be organised by INSA and GRAIE in 2023 took place on 6-7 March 2024. This change was decided because a webinar on the same topic (Routine Uncertainty Assessment in urban drainage data) was organised by INSA in 2023 and it was deemed more appropriate to organise these two events at different times.
- Based on the success of the 25th European Junior Scientist Workshop (EJSW) in 2022, Co-UDlabs agreed to support the organisation of the 26th EJSW in 2024, even though this activity was not initially part of the DoA in the GA.
- An additional workshop on UDMT, which was not planned in the GA, was organised by UDC on October 17, 2023, back-to-back with the Spanish Water Engineering Days.

Annex 1. Agenda of the 1st Early-Stage Researchers Seminar (June 27-28, 2022)

DAY 1		Monday, June 27, 2022, 16:00–19:00 (CEST)
16:00–18:00	Participants' welcome and registration	<u>UDC School of Civil Engineering</u>
19:30	Icebreaking event: <i>A Pint of Co-UDlabs</i>	'Tapas' route in the city: checkpoint at ' <u>Obelisco</u> ' landmark site downtown
DAY 2		Tuesday, June 28, 2022, 09:00–17:00 (CEST)
08:30–09:00	Participants' welcome and registration	Room 8–Ground floor, <u>UDC School of Civil Engineering</u>
09:00–09:20	Welcoming remarks and introduction to the Seminar	
	Co-UDlabs researchers' portfolio–Early-stage and senior researchers (1)	20-minute presentation of work performed on urban drainage by Co-UDlabs partners [HYBRID EVENT: LINK]
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manuel Regueiro (UDC) SedTemp: Approach to sediment accumulation in urban drainage systems based on temperature measurements
09:20–11:00		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marcel Goerke (IKT) Planning and conception of a heavy rain laboratory and its practical use Pierre Lechevallier (EAWAG) Non-contact monitoring of wastewater turbidity and organic pollution with hyperspectral camera
11:00–11:15	Coffee break	
	Co-UDlabs researchers' portfolio–Early-stage and senior researchers (2)	20-minute presentation of work performed on urban drainage by Co-UDlabs partners [HYBRID EVENT: LINK]
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Jose Anta (UDC) Permeable pavement clogging laboratory experiments using rainfall simulators
11:15–13:30		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sophie Scutt (University of Sheffield) Evaluating the Public Health Risks of Urban Flooding Events Jörg Rieckermann (EAWAG) Performance assessment of RTC of urban drainage systems based on (uncertain) monitoring data
13:30–15:00	Lunch break at ETSICCP Cafeteria	

Co-UDlabs researchers' portfolio–Early-stage and senior researchers (3)

20-minute presentation of work performed on urban drainage by Co-UDlabs partners [\[HYBRID EVENT: LINK\]](#)

15:00–16:40

- François Clemens (DELTARES)
DELTARES research on Urban Drainage Systems
- João Paulo Leitão (EAWAG)
Flooding and image-based analysis (water level estimation from images)
- Esteban Sañudo Costoya (UDC)
Hydraulic experiments and topographic survey applying LiDAR and SfM techniques at BLOCK facility

16:40–17:00

Wrap-up and closing remarks

20:00

Social dinner, Restaurante Artabria

Project-wide dinner for all ESRS and GA participants

Annex 2. Flyer of the PhD Course on Sewer Processes (October 7-11 2024)

1st announcement

2024 Ph.D. course on Sewer Processes

Modeling of sewer microbial and chemical processes

The course provides a basis for up-to-date knowledge and modeling of sewer microbial and chemical processes and shows how this understanding can be applied for design, operation, and maintenance of wastewater collection systems. A central focus of the course is on predicting critical impacts and controlling adverse effects of hydrogen sulfide and other toxic/noxious gases.

The course:

- Highlights the importance of aerobic, anoxic, and anaerobic processes
- Details the development of sewer process models
- Present new modeling tools for the design and operation of sewer networks
- The models Mega-WATS and Mega-Vent will be used throughout the course

During the course, the participants will get hands-on experience with setting up numerical sewer processes models and with designing experiments for determination of central model parameters. In addition, the course will introduce experimental methods to quantify wastewater quality in terms of biodegradability and chemical composition.

The course is aimed at Ph.D. students and sewer process specialist in the water industry.

Keywords: Sewer Odor, Concrete Corrosion, Sewer process modelling

Registration is free, but the number of seats is limited to 20. On-line registration is possible via this link: <https://phd.moodle.aau.dk/login/index.php>

The course is supported by the Horizon 2020 project Co-UDLABS. Food and drinks during the course days will be provided.

For more details contact Asbjørn Haaning Nielsen: ahn@build.aau.dk. It is encouraged to send a notification of interest including your affiliation and a short motivation for your interest in the topic.

Organizers: Asbjørn Haaning Nielsen & Jes Vollertsen

Time: October 7 – 11, 2024, Deadline for registration: 16 September 2024

Venue: AAU BUILD, Thomas Manns Vej 23, 9220 Aalborg, Denmark

ECTS: 5

Co-UDlabs
Co-ordinating Urban Drainage
Research and Learning

AALBORG
UNIVERSITY

Annex 3. Flyer of the 25th EJSW – European Junior Scientists Workshop (May 15-21, 2022)

EJSW ON 'MONITORING URBAN DRAINAGE SYSTEMS AND RIVERS'

When: 15th May – 21st May 2022
Where: Saint Maurice en Valgaudemar, France

ABSTRACT SUBMISSION
Apply: Extended abstracts should be sent not later than **9th January 2022** to the following e-mail address:
ejsw-2022@sciencesconf.org

Applications require a 1-page motivation letter, an up to 4-pages extended abstract and personal details including name, age, affiliation, position and e-mail address. All submitted abstracts will be evaluated through a scientific review. The organising committee will select the final extended abstracts (max. 24 junior participants) for oral presentations and notify the acceptance by end of January 2022.

PROMOTERS

ORGANISING COMMITTEE
 Jean-Luc BERTRAND-KRAJEWSKI (INSA Lyon)
 Francois CLEMENS (Deltares, NTNU)
 Mathieu LEPOUT (INSA Lyon)
 Oldrich NAVRATIL (Univ. Lyon, CNRS UMR 5600)
 Antonio MORENO RODENAS (Deltares)

LOCATION & VENUE
 Saint Maurice en Valgaudemar is a small typical village in the French Alps, at the entrance of the Séveraise valley, close to Ecrins National Park.
 The workshop venue is the *Val des Sources Hotel* (<http://www.levaldessources.com/en/home/>), with a meeting room and access to both a small channel and a river (with a flood every evening during that season!) a few minutes away for the practical workshop sessions.
 Surrounding landscape and nature offer possibilities for active recreation between workshop sessions. Free-time between working sessions would allow visiting the Séveraise valley, hiking, cycling, rafting, etc.

St Maurice en Valgaudemar, 1100 m altitude.
 (source: <https://www.geneanet.org>)

First Announcement & Call for Abstracts

25th European Junior Scientists Workshop

MONITORING URBAN DRAINAGE SYSTEMS AND RIVERS

Hands-on seminar on sensor applications and monitoring techniques

Saint Maurice en Valgaudemar, France
15th – 21st May 2022

Organised by
SS&PWG
 Sewer Systems & Processes Working Group of the IWA – IAHR Joint Committee on Urban Drainage

and the Co-UDlabs H2020 European Project

BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

You are a motivated young scientist, a PhD student or a starting post-doc researcher? You want to present ideas and plans, discuss preliminary results of your own research in an inspiring, open, cooperative and non-competitive environment?

Then, the European Junior Scientists Workshops (EJSWs) provide a perfect opportunity to do so. The idea is not only to listen, neither only to talk and to dominate, but to learn from and help each other in solving scientific problems in a collaborative way.

The 25th EJSW focuses on:

- On-line monitoring of water quality and quantity in waste- and stormwater collection systems, and rivers.
- Links between data validation and model calibration.
- Emerging monitoring concepts and data communication techniques.
- Ethics in researching, publishing, presenting and sharing data.

The Séveraise river (source: <https://clede.fr>).

In a plebiscite manner the 4th edition of this particular workshop offers juniors to i) **present and discuss**, and ii) **hands-on practice** of various measuring principles in a setting that gives more opportunity to learn and to share compared to regular conferences.

CALL FOR EXTENDED ABSTRACTS

Authors are invited to submit an extended abstract accompanied with a 1-page motivation letter not later than **9th January 2022**.

The extended abstract should include title, author(s), affiliation(s), full address (incl. tel. and e-mail) of the corresponding author and 3-5 keywords. The abstract should be between two and four A4-pages including a graphical abstract, illustrations, diagrams, tables and references. Objectives, hypotheses, applied approach, applicability, equipment and methods should be emphasised and (some) results should be presented.

Extended abstracts should be submitted via e-mail, preferably in MS Word format.

For the preparation of the abstracts, authors should use the instructions for authors recommended by Water Science and Technology (a template is available):

<http://wst.iwaponline.com/content/instructions-authors-wst>

Up to 23 participants will be selected based on submitted abstracts. Evaluation of abstracts will be carried out by the Organising Committee. Authors will be notified of acceptance for oral presentation not later than **31st January 2022**.

FEES

Participants are expected to make all travel arrangements to and from Lyon, France and pay for the trip. The workshop costs will be sponsored. A workshop fee of approx. € 600 (exact amount will be given on the website in January 2022) for all participants will be charged to cover costs for local transportation (Lyon Part Dieu railway station to Saint Maurice en Valgaudemar and return), accommodation and all meals.

PUBLICATION

Selected extended abstracts will be published as workshop proceedings on the workshop website with agreement of the authors.

PROGRAMME

The 25th EJSW will not only offer junior scientists an opportunity to present their research work and to be trained in chairing sessions as usual EJSWs, but will also put forward a unique set of practice sessions lead by the Organising Committee.

Participants during the EJSW 2019 edition in La Bérarde.

Morning sessions will be devoted to junior scientists' oral presentations and short lectures for afternoon sessions.

Afternoon sessions will include hands-on field workshops on the following topics:

- How to do proper sampling?
- How does a sensor work?
- Why and how to calibrate sensors?
- What induces measurement uncertainty?
- How to assess/interpret this uncertainty?
- How to analyse and validate raw data?
- How to operate a data communication network?
- How to design, to build and to maintain a monitoring station?

WEBSITES

Info and updates will be given at:

25th EJSW website:

<https://ejsw-2022.sciencesconf.org>

SS&PWG website: <http://www.sspwg.org>

Co-UDlabs website: <https://co-udlabs.eu>

Annex 4. Flyer of the 26th EJSW – European Junior Scientists Workshop (May 26 - June 1, 2024)

EJSW ON 'MONITORING URBAN DRAINAGE SYSTEMS AND RIVERS'

When: 26th May – 01st June 2024
Where: Saint Maurice en Valgaudemar, France

ABSTRACT SUBMISSION
Apply: Extended abstracts should be sent not later than **9th January 2024** to the following e-mail address:
ejsw_edition2024@gmail.com

Applications require a 1-page motivation letter, an up to 4-pages extended abstract and personal details including name, age, affiliation, position, and e-mail address. All submitted abstracts will be evaluated through a scientific review. The organising committee will select the final extended abstracts (max. 23 junior participants) for oral presentations and notify the acceptance by end of January 2024.

INSA INSTITUT NATIONAL DES SCIENCES APPLIQUÉES LYON
Deltares
université Lumière LYON 2
NTNU Norwegian University of Science and Technology

ORGANISING COMMITTEE

Jean-Luc BERTRAND-KRAJEWSKI (INSA Lyon)
Francois CLEMENS-MEYER (NTNU)
Mathieu LEPOT (INSA Lyon)
Oldrich NAVRATIL (Univ. Lyon, CNRS UMR 5600)
Antonio MORENO RODENAS (Deltares)

LOCATION & VENUE

Saint Maurice en Valgaudemar is a small typical village in the French Alps, at the entrance of the Séveraise valley, close to Echins National Park.
The workshop venue is the *Val des Sources Hotel* (<http://www.levaldessources.com/en/home/>), with a meeting room and access to both a small channel and a river (with a flood every evening during that season) a few minutes away for the practical workshop sessions.
Surrounding landscape and nature offer possibilities for active recreation between workshop sessions. Free time between working sessions would allow visiting the Séveraise valley, hiking, cycling, rafting, etc.

St Maurice en Valgaudemar, 1100 m altitude.
(source: <https://www.geneanet.org>)

2nd Announcement & Call for Abstracts

26th European Junior Scientists Workshop

MONITORING URBAN DRAINAGE SYSTEMS AND RIVERS

Hands-on seminar on sensor applications and monitoring techniques

Saint Maurice en Valgaudemar, France
26th May – 01st June 2024

Organised by
SS&PWG
Sewer Systems & Processes
Working Group of the IWA – IAHR
Joint Committee on Urban Drainage
and the Co-UDlabs H2020 European Project

Co-UDlabs

BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

You are a motivated young scientist, a PhD student or a starting post-doc researcher? You want to present ideas and plans, discuss preliminary results of your own research in an inspiring, open, cooperative and non-competitive environment?

Then, the European Junior Scientists Workshops (EJSWs) provide a perfect opportunity to do so. The idea is not only to listen, neither only to talk and to dominate, but to learn from and help each other in solving scientific problems in a collaborative way.

The 26th EJSW focuses on:

- On-line monitoring of water quality and quantity in waste- and stormwater collection systems, and rivers.
- Links between data validation and model calibration.
- Emerging monitoring concepts and data communication techniques.
- Ethics in research, publishing, presenting and sharing data.

The Séveraise river (source: <https://cleda.fr>).

In a plebiscite manner the 5th edition of this particular workshop offers juniors to i) **present and discuss**, and ii) **hands-on practice** of various measuring principles in a setting that gives more opportunity to learn and to share compared to regular conferences.

CALL FOR EXTENDED ABSTRACTS

Authors are invited to submit an extended abstract accompanied with a 1-page motivation letter not later than **9th January 2024**.

The extended abstract should include title, author(s), affiliation(s), full address (incl. tel. and e-mail) of the corresponding author and 3-5 keywords. The abstract should be between two and four A4-pages including a graphical abstract, illustrations, diagrams, tables and references. Objectives, hypotheses, applied approach, applicability, equipment and methods should be emphasised and (some) results should be presented.

Extended abstracts should be submitted via e-mail, preferably in MS Word format.

For the preparation of the abstracts, authors should use the instructions for authors recommended by Water Science and Technology (a template is available): <http://wst.iwaponline.com/content/instructions-authors-wst>

Up to 23 participants will be selected based on submitted abstracts. Evaluation of abstracts will be carried out by the Organising Committee. Authors will be notified of acceptance for oral presentation not later than **31st January 2024**.

FEES

Participants are expected to make all travel arrangements to and from Lyon, France and pay for the trip. The workshop costs will be sponsored. A workshop fee of approx. € 700 (exact amount will be given on the website in January 2024) for all participants will be charged to cover costs for local transportation (Lyon Part Dieu railway station to Saint Maurice en Valgaudemar and return), accommodation and all meals.

PUBLICATION

Selected extended abstracts will be published as workshop proceedings on the workshop website with agreement of the authors.

PROGRAMME

The 26th EJSW will not only offer junior scientists an opportunity to present their research work and to be trained in charring sessions as usual EJSWs, but will also put forward a unique set of practice sessions lead by the Organising Committee.

Participants during the EJSW 2022 edition in Saint Maurice.

Morning sessions will be devoted to junior scientist's oral presentations and short lectures for afternoon sessions.

Afternoon sessions will include hands-on field workshops on the following topics:

- How to do proper sampling?
- How does a sensor work?
- Why and how to calibrate sensors?
- What induces measurement uncertainty?
- How to assess/interpret this uncertainty?
- How to analyse and validate raw data?
- How to operate a data communication network?
- How to design, to build and to maintain a monitoring station?

WEBSITES

Info and updates will be given at:

26th EJSW website:

<https://ejsw-2024.sciencesconf.org>

SS&PWG website: <http://www.sspwg.org>

Co-UDlabs website: <https://co-udlabs.eu>

Annex 5. Agenda of the Co-UDlabs online practice workshop on urban drainage (November 3-4, 2021)

DAY 1	Wednesday 3rd November 2021, 09.00 – 12.30 (CET) / 08.00 – 11.30 (GMT/UTC)
09:00	Welcome by workshop moderator - Dr. Iain Naismith (Co-UDlabs - IKT, Germany)
The Co-UDlabs Project	
09:00 – 09:15	Why is the European Commission funding the Co-UDlabs Project? Objectives, Ambition, Work programme Dr. Iain Naismith (Co-UDlabs - IKT, Germany) Dr. Jose Anta Álvarez (Co-UDlabs - Universidade da Coruña, Spain)
09:15 – 09:30	Co-UDlabs and collaboration - Bringing Science, Industry and Network Operators together Dipl.-Ing. Thomas Brüggemann (Co-UDlabs - IKT, Germany) Prof. Dr.-Ing. Bert Bosseler (Co-UDlabs - IKT, Germany)
Setting the scene – Storm Bernd – July 2021	
09:30 – 09:45	Case Study - Heavy rainfall events in Europe in July 2021: consequences and challenges for sewer network operators (experiences of IKT in co-ordinating assistance for affected municipalities) Mirko Salomon (ComNetAbwasser - IKT, Germany)
Session I - Optimising existing urban drainage asset performance - use of monitoring and sensing to optimise network performance in response to heavy rainfall	
09:45 – 09:55	Overview of issues concerning monitoring and sensing for asset performance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> by the leader of the Co-UDlabs Joint Research Activity 1 on Smart Sensing and Monitoring in Urban Drainage Dr. Jean-Luc Bertrand-krajewski - INSA Lyon (France)
09:55 – 10:30	Short presentations of examples of good practice in Europe <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart Utilisation of Wastewater Storage capacity in sewers – Centaur Project (UK, France, Portugal) Dr. Alma Schellart (Co-UDlabs - University of Sheffield, UK) Pollution released in Combined Sewer Overflows. Monitoring challenges in traditional infrastructures of Madrid (Spain). Antonio Lastra (Canal Isabel II, Spain) Management of flow measurement data in sewers Dr. Franz Tscheikner-Gratl (Norwegian University of Science and Technology)
10:30 – 11:00	Panel discussion on research needs for 'use of monitoring and sensing to optimise performance in response to heavy rainfall'. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Virtual White Board open
11.00 – 11:15	Coffee break
Session II - Evaluation of Assets and Deterioration	
11:15 – 11:25	Overview of the evaluation of assets and deterioration issues <ul style="list-style-type: none"> by the leader of the Co-UDlabs Joint Research Activity 2 on Evaluation of assets deterioration in Urban Drainage systems Prof. Simon Tait, (Co-UDlabs, University of Sheffield, UK)

11:25 – 12:00	Short presentations of examples of good practice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application of cameras for monitoring pumping stations (Netherlands) Prof. François Clemens (Co-UDlabs - Deltares, Netherlands) • AI-based Approaches for Short- and Long-term Sewer Asset Management in Berlin (Germany) Dipl.-Ing. Matthias Riechel (Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin, Germany) • Numerical Studies about deterioration assets in Arnhem and Den Haag (Netherlands) Dr. Irene Scheperboer (IKT, Netherlands)
12:00 – 12:30	Panel discussion on research needs for ‘use of monitoring and sensing to optimise performance in response to heavy rainfall’. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual White Board open
12:30 - End of day 1	

DAY 2	Thursday 4th November 2021, 09.00 – 12.00 (CET) / 08.00 – 11.00 (GMT/UTC)
09:00	Welcome by workshop moderator - Dr. Iain Naismith (Co-UDlabs - IKT, German)
Session III – Improving resilience and sustainability of urban drainage assets	
09:05 – 09:15	Overview of the issues concerning resilience and sustainability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • by the leader of the Co-UDlabs Joint Research Activity 3 on Improving resilience and sustainability in urban drainage solutions Dr. Luís Cea Gómez - Universidade da Coruña (Spain)
09:15 – 10:15	Short Presentations of good practice in Europe <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dealing with London’s legacy of combined sewers (UK) Andrew Hagger (Thames Water Utilities, UK) • Development of modular technology for handling and treating rainwater as part of Aalborg Utility’s rainwater management (Denmark) Prof. Jesper Ellerbæk Nielsen (Aalborg University, Denmark) • Addressing climate change in the City of Almere (Netherlands) Maria Rus (City of Almere, Netherlands) • Co-Designing a “Livable Street”: Project ‘LesSON’ and the Future Initiative “Water in the City of Tomorrow” (Germany) Dr. Daniela Falter (Emschergenossenschaft, Germany) • Not all SuDS are created equal: Impact of different approaches on combined sewer overflows (Switzerland) Dr. Joao Paulo Leitao (Co-UDlabs - EAWAG, Switzerland)
10:15 – 11:45	Panel discussion on research needs for “Improving resilience and sustainability of urban drainage assets” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual White Board open
10:45 – 11:00	Coffee break
Reminder of the outcomes from Day 1	
11:00 – 11:15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Illustrated summary of the key points from the presentations and discussions from Day 1 – Sessions I and II Dr. Iain Naismith (Co-UDlabs – IKT, Germany)
The way forward	

11:15 – 11:55	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Panel discussion on the next steps for actioning the workshop’s findings through Co-UDlabs Co-UDlabs Joint Research Activity leaders
11:55 – 12:00	Concluding remarks
12:00 - End of day 2	

Annex 6. Agenda of the Deltares course on hydraulic capacity problems in pressurized systems (November 17, 2022)

Thursday 17th November 2022, 10.00 – 14.00 (CET)	
10:00	Welcome by course moderator – Femke Verhaart (Deltares)
10:05-12:00	<p>Introduction to the course Femke Verhaart (Deltares)</p> <p>Basic hydraulics of pressurized systems Dr. Mike van Meerkerk (Deltares)</p> <p>Identifying capacity problems Michiel Tukker (Deltares)</p> <p>Air pockets Michiel Tukker (Deltares)</p> <p>Plenary discussion and questions</p>
12:00-13:00	Lunch break
13:00-14:00	<p>Examples from the engineering practice Case 1</p> <p>Case 2</p> <p>Femke Verhaart (Deltares)</p> <p>Plenary discussion and questions</p>
14:00	Concluding remarks and post course chat

Annex 7. Agenda of the Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox workshop (October 17, 2023)

Curso sobre buenas prácticas para la monitorización de caudales y contaminación

17 de octubre de 2023

Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena (UPCT), Cartagena

PROGRAMA DEL CURSO	MARTES 17 DE OCTUBRE, 10:30 – 16:30
10.30 – 10.45	Recepción de asistentes
10.45 – 12.00	<p>BLOQUE 1 :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentación del proyecto Co-UDlabs y sus actividades relacionadas con la monitorización y la metrología. • Fundamentos de los métodos implementados en la herramienta UDMT (Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox) de análisis y tratamiento de datos obtenidos por sistemas de monitorización.
12.00 – 12.30	Pausa café
12.30 – 14.00	<p>BLOQUE 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentación de la herramienta UDMT. • Caso práctico 1: uso de la herramienta UDMT para el análisis de datos reales procedentes de un contador con telelectura.
14.00 – 15.00	Pausa comida
15.00 – 16.30	<p>BLOQUE 3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caso práctico 2: uso de la herramienta UDMT para el análisis de datos reales procedentes de una sonda de turbidez en continuo. • Discusión de casos prácticos con asistentes.

Contacto:

- Jose Anta (jose.anta@udc.es)
- Juan Naves (juan.naves@udc.es)
- Manuel Regueiro (manuel.regueiro1@udc.es)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008626

Annex 8. Flyer of the Professional Training course “Uncertainty Assessment in Urban Drainage monitoring” (March 6-7, 2024)

Co-UDlabs

graie
Groupe de Recherche en
Analyse et Modélisation
des Infrastructures Urbaines

INSA INSTITUT NATIONAL
DES SCIENCES
APPLIQUÉES
DE LYON

Professional Training course Uncertainty Assessment in Urban Drainage monitoring

Practical information

- > March 6 & 7, 2024
- > Campus de la Doua (Villeurbanne, France)
- > Language: English only
- > Limited to 15 participants

Participation fees

- > Normal rate: 180.00€
- > Graie members: 60.00€
- > Graie "committed" members: 0€

Objectives

This meeting will focus on the importance of uncertainty assessment in the monitoring of drainage systems. The lecturer will present the Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox (UDMT), provide examples of its application and answer any questions you may have in a question-and-answer session. One session will be devoted entirely to examples and case studies provided by participants.

At the end of the training: participants will be familiar with the methods applied in the UDMT tool and will know how to use it for their own needs.

Prerequisites

- > Experience in monitoring in the field of urban drainage (sewers, overflows, rainfall, pollutant discharges, including monitoring of stormwater management works at source, etc.).
- > Participants should bring their own **laptops** to the session.

Lecturer : [Jean-Luc Bertrand Krajewski](#)

 Formation professionnelle proposée par le Graie, enregistré sous le numéro 84692718469. Cet enregistrement ne vaut pas agrément de l'Etat.

 Formation Co-UDLabs organisée en partenariat avec le Graie et l'INSA Lyon.

Programme

1-Wednesday, March 6 | Morning

- General introduction
- Quick round of participants
- Lectures on uncertainty assessment (UA) (0.5 day):
 - Interest and importance of uncertainty assessment for data validation in urban drainage
 - Link with best practices in metrology, data validation and quality assurance
- Presentation of the international standards (Guide of Uncertainty in Measurements by the JCGM – Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology)
- Presentation of the methods of uncertainty assessment (statistical analysis Type A and B, and Monte Carlo method)

2 – Wednesday, March 6 | Afternoon

- Demonstration with examples in urban drainage of The UDMT – Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox – developed in the **H2020 project CO-UDlabs**, which is a Matlab/Octave open source codes that make calculation of measurements much more easy (0.25 day)
- Guided exercise for the participants, with correction (0.25 day).

3 – Thursday, March 7

Training and application by participants who will bring their own cases and data sets (1 day).

Formation professionnelle proposée par le Graie, enregistré sous le numéro 84692118469. Cet enregistrement ne vaut pas agrément de l'Etat.

Formation Co-UDLabs organisée en partenariat avec le Graie et l'INSA Lyon.

Annex 9. Agenda of the Webinar on Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) chemical mapping (July 16-19, 2024)

Applied Course on Urban Drainage Metrology

Daily schedule

- Morning Session: 09:30 – 13:30 CEST
- Lunch break at the facility
- Afternoon Session: 15:30 – 17:30 CEST

Module 1 – Tuesday, July 16, 2024

- **Measurement of hydraulic variables.** Rainfall, flow rates, water depths, and velocities will be measured using different technologies (direct measurement, ultrasound, pressure, acoustic velocimetry, etc.)

Module 2 – Wednesday, July 17, 2024

- **Measurement of pollution parameters.** Automatic grab samplers and on-line probes will be used to measure the most relevant variables and methods of analysis

Module 3 – Thursday, July 18, 2024

- **Data collection and management.** In this session different technologies to convert signals to data will be presented. Additionally, the course will present how parametrize hydraulic and pollution parameters link to dry and wet weather flows

Module 4 – Friday, July 19, 2024

- **Demo Day – Simulation of a field campaign in the infrastructure of CITEEC.** Field work will be simulated in the BLOCK model and SUDS pilot techniques. Measurements of all relevant parameters will be carried out, both online and with grab samples

 Co-UDlabs receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101008626

Annex 10. Agenda of the Webinar on Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) chemical mapping (September 21, 2022)

Wednesday 21st September 2022, 14.00 – 15:30 (CEST)	
PART 1	
14:00 – 14:25	FTIR theory... a quick intro How an FTIR spectrometer work? A few definitions From Marco to μ FTIR μ FTIR microscopy μ FTIR Chemical Mapping... How does it work?
14:25	5 min break
PART 2	
14:30 – 15:00	FPA Chemical Imaging Main applications of μ FTIR Chemical mapping μ FTIR Imaging and urban drainage: analysis of microplastics in urban waters Wrap up
15:00 – 15:30	Q&A
15:30 - End of the webinar	

Annex 11. Flyer including the agenda of the Webinar on the principles and applications of acoustic backscattering to monitor suspended solids in natural and engineered systems (May 16, 2023)

Acoustic monitoring of suspended solids in natural and engineered systems

Webinar, 16 May 2023, 13:00-16:30 CEST

Eawag
Das Wasserforschungsinstitut
des ETH-Bereichs

The Co-UDlabs project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008626.

Acoustic monitoring of suspended solids in natural and engineered systems

Co-UDLabs Webinar, 16. May 2023

Goal

Water quality is becoming increasingly important in natural and sewer environments due to sediment-related issues like erosion, transport, and deposition. These problems affect engineered systems, and the environment by causing mechanical obstacles and pollutants attached to sediments.

Total suspended solids (TSS) is a crucial parameter to monitor pollutant levels, but few techniques offer real-time data. Traditional methods involve lab measurements or optical backscatter sensors that require significant calibration and maintenance. However, acoustic turbidity monitoring, based on acoustic backscattering, offers a modern approach to TSS monitoring.

In this webinar we will discuss the latest developments in TSS monitoring using acoustic backscattering methods, including fundamental principles, particle characteristics, instrument calibration, signal analysis, and inversion methods. Practical experiences from monitoring in rivers and wastewater systems will also be shared, as well as limitations of the technique and potential for further development.

Target audience

The webinar is aimed at engineers, planners, and operators of wastewater systems, representatives of municipalities and authorities, as well as manufacturers of monitoring equipment, who would like to gain further insight into modern technologies for environmental monitoring.

Date, Time, Place

Tuesday, 16. May 2023, 13:00 – 16:30 CEST
online

Contact and registration

www.Co-UDLabs.eu
info@co-udlabs.eu
Registration:
<https://forms.office.com/e/td6294dJmN>
Participation is free.

Program

- 13:00 Welcome and introduction**
Jörg Rieckermann, Eawag, CH
- 13:05 The importance of particles and continuous monitoring in urban drainage systems**
Peter Vanrolleghem, Université Laval, CA
- 13:20 Acoustic Scattering from particles - theory and scientific instruments**
Stephane Fischer, Ubertone S.A.S., F
- 13:35 Experimental evaluation of hydro-acoustic models and inversion methods in rivers**
Céline Berni, INRAE, F
- 13:50 Discussion**
- 14:25 Coffee break**
- 15:00 Monitoring suspended solids with acoustic turbidity in sewers**
Asmorom Kibrom, NIVUS GmbH, D
- 15:15 Lab-scale characterization of TSS using acoustic backscattering**
Manuel A. Regueiro Picallo, University of A Coruña, ES
- 15:30 Experiences with acoustic monitoring of fine TSS for stormwater treatment**
Daniela Böckmann, Dr. Pecher AG, D
- 15:45 Time Resolved Optical Turbidity**
Anne Pallarès, Université de Strasbourg, F
- 16:00 Discussion**
- 16:30 End**

Annex 12. Agenda of the Webinar on Optical observations in urban water systems and rivers (March 15, 2024)

Optical observations in urban water systems and rivers

Webinar 15 March 2024
9:30-12:00 CET

Goal

This webinar presents recent advances in the application of optical imaging techniques for monitoring water quantity/quality dynamics and hydraulic structures. We will present several state-of-the-art large-scale PIV techniques for flow estimations in rivers, urban infrastructure, and different AI-assisted data processing routines to extract information on the hydro-environment.

Target audience

This webinar is aimed at researchers, engineers, planners, and operators of water systems, representatives of municipalities and authorities, as well as manufacturers of monitoring equipment, who would like to gain further insight optically-based environmental monitoring in rivers and urban water infrastructure.

Date, Time, Place

Friday, 15 March 2024, 9:30– 12:00CET
Online

Contacts

www.co-udlabs.eu
info@co-udlabs.eu

Registration:

[REGISTER HERE](#)

Participation is free.

Program

9:30	Welcome and introduction Dr. Antonio Moreno-Rodenas, Deltares
9:35	Large-scale PIV in urban structures Dr. Juan Naves, Universidad de Coruña
9:50	Open source image-based velocimetry in rivers Dr. Hessel Winsemius, Deltares/Rainbow Sensing
10:05	Image-based discharge measurements in sewers Dr. Salvador Peña-Haro, Photrack
10:20	Using water surface waves for discharge monitoring in rivers Dr. Giulio Dolcetti, University of Trento
10:35	Coffee-Break
10:45	Deep-learning for hydro-environmental applications Dr. Antonio Moreno-Rodenas, Deltares
11:00	Deep-learning for sewer pipeline defect classification Prof. Simon Tait, University of Sheffield
11:15	Estimation of flood water-depth from social media imagery Ass Prof. Joao Leitao, EAWAG/ETH
11:30	An introduction to non-contact wastewater quality monitoring with hyperspectral camera Pierre Lechevallier / Dr. Jorg Rieckermann EAWAG
11:45	Discussion and Closure

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